

SEPTEMBER 2023

THE ROLE OF CARBON CAPTURE AND UTILISATION IN THE PATH TO NET ZERO:

RECOMMENDATIONS FROM THE *CO2MOS* PROJECT

Prepared by COZMOS project partners

TATA STEEL

 SINTEF

UNIVERSITÀ
DEGLI STUDI
DI TORINO

 **University of
Sheffield**

In collaboration with

UGI
INTERNATIONAL

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 837733

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

To limit global warming to below 1.5°C, global net anthropogenic CO₂ emissions need to reach net zero around 2050. There are several ways to reduce global CO₂ emissions, such as improving energy efficiency, increasing renewable energy production, electrification, using high energy density molecules as an alternative to fossil ones, and capturing CO₂ from power plants and other emission points¹⁻². For the first time, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change, in its 6th Assessment Report released in 2022³, recognised Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) as one of the solutions to mitigate climate change. Several forecasts for the chemical industry show CCU will contribute 10-30% of the demand for embedded carbon in 2050⁴.

Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) refers to the capture and conversion of CO₂ into products, e.g. fuels, chemicals and building materials. Some of the products that cannot be used directly as a fuel, can be used as intermediates to produce other fuels such as diesel, gasoline and aviation fuels that are compatible with existing infrastructure. The substitution of fossil-based products by CO₂-based ones reduces CO₂ emissions, even if the technology is not emission-negative by itself and if the CO₂ is emitted after the combustion⁵.

COZMOS is a Horizon 2020-funded project that aims to provide breakthrough technology for converting CO₂ to fuels. The project has developed an innovative catalyst that overcomes the thermodynamic limitations inherent in using CO₂ for these value-added products. COZMOS, a 4-year programme, was launched in 2019 and is due to finish in October 2023, involving industrial partners from the steel, refining, chemical and engineering sectors, research and technology organisations and universities.

The COZMOS process can produce CO₂-based propane. The propane market is expected to continue growing. Thus, if propane could be derived from CO₂, this could reduce fossil fuel use. Propane is a fuel currently found in lighters, aerosol deodorants, propane gas fireplaces, propane cooking stoves, grills, barbeques and outdoor kitchens, and camping and caravanning gas. The COZMOS project has tested the catalyst at pilot plant scale in a refinery setting, conducted a Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) and techno-economic assessment of the technology, and assessed the public's acceptance of CCU technologies.

This paper will highlight recommendations arising from the COZMOS project for CCU to play a meaningful role in the transition to net zero. It will cover the main benefits of implementing CCU, the current CCU policy landscape and recommendations from the COZMOS project for policymakers, university/researchers and LCA practitioners, separately. The next section summarises the key recommendations.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR POLICYMAKERS

1. Address decarbonisation and defossilisation of all sectors that require carbon as a feedstock. Decarbonisation implies an elimination of carbon from an economic activity or industrial process, it describes the transformation of industries, particularly the energy sector, to cut CO₂ emissions and eventually reach “net zero” and an emission-free society. Defossilisation involves becoming independent of fossil raw materials.
2. Consider the full carbon cycle and carbon ownership.
3. Introduce a feed-in transition for CO₂-based fuels.
4. Provide funding for universities and industry to collaborate and work on the technology bottlenecks and address the funding disconnect in funding for low and high technology readiness level projects.
5. Improve communication in order to increase the public awareness and acceptance of the technology.
6. Encourage the assessment of each CCU pathway and technology considering the full life cycle impacts.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UNIVERSITIES/RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS

1. Identify which technologies and products would be most useful to society, in collaboration with industry.
2. Improve the current production of hydrogen and the energy efficiency of water electrolysis.
3. Focus on increasing the technology readiness level of these technologies so they become commercially available.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR LCA PRACTITIONERS

1. Positively recognise the benefits of reusing CO₂ and the substitution of fossil carbon.
2. Account for benefits between CO₂-producer and CO₂-user.
3. Consider the carbon footprint of the CO₂ supply.

COZMOS PILOT PLANT

COZMOS catalyst

COZMOS pilot plant hosted at Tüpraş, in Izmit, Turkey.

BACKGROUND INFORMATION

INTRODUCTION TO CCU

Carbon Capture and Utilisation (CCU) involves capturing CO₂ from industrial processes or directly from the atmosphere and then utilising it for various applications, such as making synthetic fuels, chemicals, and building materials. This process reduces greenhouse gas emissions and creates value from CO₂, which would otherwise be emitted.

A wide range of chemicals and materials can be derived from CO₂, for example, solvents, plastics, fibres, and synthetic rubber. It can also be used in the process of making concrete, asphalt, and other building materials.

The CCU process offers an opportunity to create value from CO₂, which can have economic benefits for industries that use it as a raw material. CCU is an emerging field with enormous potential to contribute to the transition to a low-carbon economy, and it is receiving increasing attention from policymakers, scientists and businesses worldwide.

CCU vs CCS

CCU and Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) are two technologies aimed at mitigating climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions. Often, CCS is used interchangeably with the term CCU⁶. Grouping both terms does not reflect their different approaches.

CCS focuses on capturing carbon dioxide and storing it in underground geological formations, preventing its release into the atmosphere. CCS is widely recognised as supporting decarbonisation, allowing continued use of fossil-fuelled power plants whilst reducing CO₂ emissions⁷⁻⁸. On the other hand, CCU aims to capture carbon dioxide and convert it into usable products, such as building materials or synthetic fuels, thereby providing an opportunity to create value from CO₂ emissions. CCU also reduces the use of fossil carbon (e.g., coal, natural gas) for these products (also known as “defossilisation”).

While CCS and CCU can potentially reduce carbon emissions, the two approaches have different benefits and limitations. The long-term storage of CO₂ underground is an end-of-pipe solution. Additionally, the deployment of CCS is influenced by a range of policy and regulatory factors, which vary across different regions and countries. In some regions, the lack of a clear policy framework or regulatory incentives for CCS deployment can limit its adoption. In contrast, CCU has the potential to create value by using CO₂ as a feedstock, but the technology is still in its early stages⁹.

CCU is a complement to CCS for large-scale emission reductions, both will play a role in the transition to a low-carbon economy¹⁰. Ultimately, both CCS and CCU are important tools in the fight against climate change, and their deployment will depend on each country or region’s specific needs and circumstances.

BENEFITS OF IMPLEMENTING CCU

A SOLUTION FOR HARD-TO-ABATE SECTORS

Significant efforts have been made to reduce global CO₂ emissions across all sectors. These include improving process efficiencies, electrification and using non-fossil feedstocks where possible. However, the emission reduction potential of process efficiency improvements is insufficient to reach Net Zero. Similarly, electrification is not possible or feasible in hard-to-abate sectors (e.g. steel, petrochemicals, aluminium, cement and fertilisers). Heavy industries account for over 20% of global CO₂ emissions today¹¹. CCU could be a cost-effective approach to decarbonise cement, iron and steel and defossilise chemicals manufacturing.

Many applications will still require high energy density molecules. These include shipping, aviation, feedstock for chemistry and storage of renewable energy. Fuels from biomass or waste streams can be used as drop-in alternatives in existing systems. However, contrary to CO₂, there is a limited amount and availability of biomass and waste feedstocks. Within the transport sector, CO₂ represents one of the few feedstocks for sustainable fuels for long-distance transport, particularly aviation.

Green hydrogen is another high energy density alternative. Global hydrogen use is forecast to increase exponentially in the near future. In the Sustainable Development Scenario, the International Energy Agency predicts a sevenfold increase by 2070¹². The majority of the low-carbon hydrogen production is from water electrolysis, but it requires significant amounts of renewable energy. In 2070, 40% of low-carbon hydrogen production is predicted to come from fossil sources, with carbon capture¹². CCU can support the rapid deployment of low-carbon hydrogen production. This production can be quickly scaled up to support the growing needs from transport, industry and buildings. However, hydrogen is challenging to transport and store, and its introduction into existing infrastructure is limited, up to 20%vol can be blended into the gas pipeline network without modifications. CCU also supports the upscaling of renewable energy, as it enables the storage of surplus energy in energy carriers, such as Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG) which are easier to store and transport than hydrogen.

Due to these limitations, there will be significant residual CO₂ emissions after different decarbonisation strategies have been implemented¹³, and some sectors will continue to emit CO₂. Even in a low-carbon European economy, one-fifth of today's CO₂ could still be produced, around 346 Mt of potential feedstock CO₂¹⁴. **CCU represents an alternative for the production of high energy density molecules. However, it should not use CO₂ from sources where low-carbon alternatives are possible, only residual emissions from hard-to-abate sectors.**

CCU IS ALIGNED WITH A CIRCULAR ECONOMY

While CO₂ emissions must be reduced to reach climate mitigation targets, a holistic system approach is needed to make manufacturing more sustainable. **Other sustainability issues need to be considered, such as global supply chains, circularity of materials, reusability and recyclability.** A circular economy is complementary to reducing emissions, as it could avoid the negative consequences of focusing exclusively on CO₂ emissions and having a "carbon tunnel vision" ¹⁶.

Continuing business as usual and emitting carbon into the atmosphere is no longer an option. However, the current strategy proposed in many sectors involves the capturing and permanent storage of CO₂. This approach can be equated to landfill in a linear economy. Finding sustainable carbon sources will be key for circular and sustainable manufacturing. The capture and utilisation of CO₂ as a feedstock from an emission point source supports this idea. This approach both reduces CO₂ emissions and promotes a circular economy. Implementing CCU can support in closing the material loop. Reusing the CO₂ molecule a single time could result in up to 50% emission reduction, as it would prevent a fossil molecule from being extracted from the ground.

It is important to emphasise that CCU can only provide these benefits when powered with renewable energy. Most CCU processes need large amounts of renewable energy, directly or indirectly, in the form of green hydrogen. Using renewable energy for CCU is a sensible application in the chemicals and materials sectors, aviation, and shipping. As for these applications, there are no alternatives to using carbon in the molecules or viable carbon-free alternatives.

CONTINUED USE OF EXISTING INFRASTRUCTURE

CCU technology can be retrofitted to existing emission points such as power and industrial plants. It would enable the continued use of oil and gas pipelines, as well as liquified natural gas (LNG) terminals and tankers. CCU could provide the basic platform chemicals to the chemical industry¹⁵. Power and industrial plants could otherwise emit 600 billion tonnes of CO₂ over the next five decades⁶. When the CO₂ is captured and utilised, the CO₂-based products can be easily introduced into the existing infrastructure, without the need to fund a new infrastructure system. Additionally, it would reduce dependency on imports for these products, strengthening energy security.

CCU CAN SUPPORT DECARBONISATION, BUT THERE IS NO SINGLE SOLUTION TO THE PROBLEM

A range of complementary technologies will be needed to reach climate change targets and cover end-users' needs. CCU represents a robust solution for residual emissions from hard-to-abate sectors.

CURRENT CCU POLICY LANDSCAPE

CCU is an emerging field with large potential to contribute to the transition to a low-carbon economy, and it is receiving increasing attention in recent years. This section will provide a short overview of legislation impacting CCU in Europe, the UK and the USA.

The following policies and initiatives are in place or under discussion impacting CCU in the EU:

- The Emission Trading Scheme (ETS) considers captured CO₂ from processes as "emitted". The only exception is when the captured CO₂ is permanently stored. The current EU ETS scheme does not account for any climate benefits from CCU. However, the latest revision will allow for GHG emission reduction when CCU is applied for mineralisation or products that provide long-term storage, such as construction materials¹⁷.
- The Net-Zero Industry Act¹⁸ attempts to reduce import dependence on critical technologies. It presents CCUS as a key "net-zero technology" and makes provisions for supporting CCUS technologies below a TRL of 8.
- The Renewable Energy Directive (RED II) includes targets for Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin (RFNBO) and considers Recycled Carbon Fuels (RCF) for emission reductions in the transport sector. RFNBOs are fuels such as green hydrogen, methanol or e-fuels produced with renewable energy, providing at least a 70% reduction in GHG emissions. RCFs are fuels produced from either a waste stream of non-renewable origin or from waste and exhaust gases of non-renewable origin (such as CCU of industrial point sources).

- The Fuel EU Maritime¹⁹ and ReFuelEU proposal²⁰⁻²¹ also include targets for RFNBOs for shipping and aviation, respectively.
- The Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) addresses carbon leakage and may incentivise CCU products with long-term storage²².
- Within the Science-Based Targets initiative (SBTI) and depending on the permanence of storage and allocation of the savings, CCU can be classed as an emission reduction or Beyond Value Chain Mitigation²³.
- In March 2023, the European Union approved the use of e-fuels in cars as an exemption to its previous ban on internal combustion engines from 2035. This change sends a clear signal that synthetic fuels made from captured CO₂ can support the defossilisation of the transport sector.
- More generally, there is support for creating a more circular economy, to which CCU can contribute. The European Green Deal, launched in 2019, considers the production of products that can be repaired, recycled and re-used²⁴. The Circular Economy Action Plan proposed in 2020 aims to "make sustainable products the norm in the EU, ensure less waste, focus on the sectors...where the potential for circularity is high"²⁵. The EU has also outlined its plans for scaling up the manufacturing of crucial clean technologies to bolster the bloc's competitiveness and reduce its reliance on imports from China.

In a UK context, the UK Government launched a set of calls to investigate CCUS in the UK²⁶⁻²⁷. However, the announcement of the sixth Carbon Budget in April 2021 stated that "setting this budget is about the government's ambition to cut emissions, rather than announcing specific policies that will deliver that reduction in emissions. We will bring forward policies to meet Carbon Budgets"²⁸. **It will be key to set specific policies to drive change towards decarbonisation and defossilisation, and reduce dependence on fossil fuels.** More recently, the UK government pledged to invest up to £20bn from its spring budget 2023 to support CCUS, as part of its Net Zero Innovation Portfolio CCUS Innovation Programme²⁹. It is expected to deploy two industrial CCUS clusters by the mid-2020s (track 1) and a further two by 2030 (track 2) to achieve its CO₂ capture goal. In late 2021, it selected the HyNet and East Coast Clusters for track 1 development.

In the USA, the Inflation Reduction Act has extended the tax credits for direct air capture³⁰, which complements funding in the Bipartisan Infrastructure law for CCUS³¹, including \$2.5 billion for the *Carbon Capture Demonstration Projects Program* and \$937 million for *Carbon Capture Large-Scale Pilot Programs*. More recently, President Biden announced a \$100 million grant program to jumpstart carbon recycling. It will cover technologies like CCU that transform waste emissions into valuable resources³².

Recent policies have started to identify CCU as a key decarbonisation technology. However, current policies are lagging and are rather fragmented. The treatment of CCU as a technology is inconsistent across policies. More consistency and ambition are needed to deploy this technology. The strong focus on net zero tends to disregard the future needs for carbon as feedstock and only focuses on zero-carbon energy and carbon storage of residual emissions. **Adequately accounting for the climate benefits of CCU would incentivise this valuable technology and provide a clear regulatory framework for deployment.** This would reduce investment uncertainty and accelerate commercialisation. It is recognised that the cost of CO₂-based products will be higher than fossil-based products, so will need subsidies and incentives to regulate the costs to the end-user. This investment is expected to come initially from governments.

The learnings from the COZMOS project have been distilled into a number of recommendations for policymakers, universities and research institutions and LCA practitioners. The recommendations are shown in the following pages.

RECOMMENDATIONS FROM THE COZMOS PROJECT

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR POLICYMAKERS

In order to reduce emissions and promote a circular economy across all sectors, holistic thinking has to be implemented into policies. Recognising that a mix of technologies will be needed to reach Net Zero is required. The combination of hydrogen and electrification is insufficient to complete the transition, and alternative technologies will be needed. While the focus of policies should be on decarbonising as much as possible, developing CCU technologies in parallel as a solution for residual emissions will help to achieve our climate targets.

1. More specific policies are needed, **focusing on improving circularity** and including CCU as an important tool to support this.

2. Introduce policies that **address decarbonisation and defossilisation of all sectors that require carbon as a feedstock**, such as the chemical and materials sector, which will continue to require carbon as a feedstock. Decarbonisation implies an elimination of carbon from an economic activity or industrial process, it describes the transformation of industries, particularly the energy sector, to cut CO₂ emissions and eventually reach „net zero” and an emission-free society. Defossilisation involves becoming independent of fossil raw materials.

3. Another aspect to be considered in policies is the **full carbon cycle and ownership**. Moving towards a carbon custodianship model would increase the public's awareness of the carbon origin and destinations. It would also help increase consumer responsibility for purchased energy and goods, and indirectly reduce emissions via a behavioural change. A sense of responsibility from individuals and groups is required to ensure equity in society³⁵.

4. Any policies looking to support CCU would benefit from **introducing a feed-in transition**, where CO₂-based fuels and products are progressively incentivised while carbon-intensive fuels are disincentivised.

5. **Funding is required for universities and industry to collaborate and work on the technology bottlenecks**. And although funding exists to progress projects from low technology readiness levels (TRL), many projects are not reaching TRL 9. Long-term vision is needed to filter and funnel the projects as they progress in TRL; however, this is currently lacking. **There is a disconnect in funding for low TRL and higher TRL projects**, both in technologies and in the size of funding.

6. Currently, public awareness and knowledge of CCU is low, making the public sensitive to framing and bound to the agenda of communicators, whether it's to support or oppose a technology³⁴. **Improving public communication and engaging with relevant stakeholders would increase the public awareness** of the technology and the transparency of CCU projects.

7. **Each CCU pathway and technology should be assessed considering the full life cycle impacts**, ideally including the entire supply chain and lifetime of the product. This would ensure that the technology is fit for purpose and would be adequate for tackling residual emissions and promoting a more circular economy.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UNIVERSITIES/RESEARCH INSTITUTIONS

1. In order to prioritise which technologies should be developed and progressed, it is key for universities to collaborate with both industry and governments. This collaboration will help **identify which technologies and products would be most useful to society** and work on finding solutions to the different technology and environmental bottlenecks. A knowledge transfer between disciplines and sectors is needed to develop these processes and accelerate their implementation.

2. One of the key bottlenecks for the COZMOS technology is the need for hydrogen in the feed. It is added to the feed to convert the CO₂ to propane. This significantly affects the economic and environmental performance of the process. **Improving the current production of hydrogen or improving the energy efficiency of water electrolysis would benefit the economic and environmental performance of CCU processes.**

3. According to the IEA, 75% of the emissions reductions needed will come from a range of technologies currently in development³⁵. Further research can **increase the technology readiness level of these technologies** so they become commercially available. Universities have a key role to play in further developing these technologies.

RECOMMENDATIONS FOR LCA PRACTITIONERS

Life Cycle Assessments (LCAs) are invaluable tools to understand the broader implications of a technology beyond climate change, considering factors such as resource depletion. It helps to identify and mitigate unintended consequences, ensuring a holistic understanding of the impacts and benefits associated with a product or process.

The climate benefits associated with CCU will depend on several factors, like the source of CO₂ and energy for capture, the displaced product, and the retention of CO₂ in the final product. Utilising CO₂ does not necessarily reduce the climate change impacts. A robust life cycle assessment is needed to quantify the climate benefits of CCU. There have been several attempts at developing LCA guidelines for CCU⁵⁻³⁶, within the context of ISO 14044, but there are still gaps to be addressed for a robust LCA of CCU technologies. **A harmonised approach for accounting for the impacts of CCU technology would support in clarifying the benefits and incentivising the technology.**

The following are recommendations for LCA practitioners:

1. Positively recognise the benefits of reusing CO₂ and the substitution of fossil carbon.

Reusing carbon is an approach toward closing the anthropogenic carbon cycle and a circular value chain. Most studies consider the CO₂ reductions if the process emissions for the CCU process are lower than those from the extraction of coal, gas or oil and disregard the benefits of substituting a fossil feedstock. In line with a life cycle approach, expanded system boundaries, cradle-to-gate or cradle-to-grave, should be used to account for the benefit of reusing the CO₂, and these should be clearly communicated. There is a net carbon benefit to using CO₂ twice before releasing it into the atmosphere.

2. Accounting for benefits between CO₂-producer and CO₂-user.

The direct emissions are reduced when the CO₂ is captured at an emission point source. There will be additional GHG emissions from the capture and utilisation process. The CO₂ becomes a co-product of the original CO₂-emitting process. Additionally, when the captured CO₂ is utilised and converted into a value-added product, the CO₂-based product also becomes a co-product from the original process. This attribution of credits between the CO₂-producer and the CO₂-user is complex. Depending on how the LCA system boundaries are set, there will be different discussions on how to allocate the environmental benefits of the overall process. When considering the CO₂-producer, the carbon footprint associated with the captured CO₂ becomes relevant. According to Müller et al.¹⁴, the emissions associated with the feedstock CO₂ should be the difference between increased emissions and avoided emissions.

3. Accounting consistently for the carbon footprint of the CO₂ supply will be key.

The emissions reduction from CCU strongly depends on the choice of CO₂ source, as the CO₂ concentration and energy demand for capturing it will differ. CO₂ sources with a high concentration of CO₂ should be prioritised for CCU to optimise the energy used in the capture process. In previous studies, the carbon footprint of the captured CO₂ varied from strongly negative to strongly positive for the same emission point source¹⁴. This inconsistency is linked to methodological choices in the LCA studies; however, it is key that the carbon footprint of the CO₂ supply is correctly accounted for. Müller et al.¹⁴ recommend adhering to physical relationships to assess the carbon footprint of the supply of CO₂. They refer to physical relationships as the marginal changes needed for adding CO₂ capture and transportation to existing operations and their associated GHG emissions. They recommend assessing the system-wide impacts using system expansion or product-specific environmental impacts with the substitution approach. Allocation by mass or economic value was discouraged as it would lead to suboptimal decisions.

REFERENCES

1. Nunez, C. (2019, May 13). Carbon dioxide levels are at a record high. Here's what you need to know. National Geographic. <https://www.nationalgeographic.com/environment/article/greenhouse-gases>
2. Mertens, J., Belmans, R., & Webber, M. (2020). Why the Carbon-Neutral Energy Transition Will Imply the Use of Lots of Carbon. *C – Journal of Carbon Research*, 6(2), 39. <https://doi.org/10.3390/c6020039>
3. IPCC. (2023). Synthesis report for the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (AR6). In Diriba Korecha Dadi. Panmao Zhai.
4. Kähler, F., & Carus, M. (2023). Compilation of supply and demand of fossil and renewable carbon on a global and European level RENEWABLE CARBON INITIATIVE REPORT. www.renewable-carbon-initiative.com
5. Langhorst, T., McCord, S., Zimmermann, A., Müller, L., Cremonese, L., Strunge, T. W. Y., Zaragoza, A. V., Wunderlich, J., Marxen, A., Armstrong, K., Buchner, G., Kätelhön, A., Bachmann, M., Sternberg, A., Michailos, S., Naims, H., Winter, B., Roskosch, D., Faber, G., ... Sick, V. (2022). Techno-Economic Assessment & Life Cycle Assessment Guidelines for CO₂ Utilization (version 2.0). <https://doi.org/10.7302/4190>
6. IEA. (2021, April). About CCUS. <https://www.iea.org/reports/about-ccus>
7. Bui, M., Adjiman, C. S., Bardow, A., Anthony, E. J., Boston, A., Brown, S., Fennell, P. S., Fuss, S., Galindo, A., Hackett, L. A., Hallett, J. P., Herzog, H. J., Jackson, G., Kemper, J., Krevor, S., Maitland, G. C., Matuszewski, M., Metcalfe, I. S., Petit, C., ... mac Dowell, N. (2018). Carbon capture and storage (CCS): the way forward. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 11(5), 1062–1176. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C7EE02342A>
8. Boot-Handford, M. E., Abanades, J. C., Anthony, E. J., Blunt, M. J., Brandani, S., mac Dowell, N., Fernández, J. R., Ferrari, M. C., Gross, R., Hallett, J. P., Haszeldine, R. S., Heptonstall, P., Lyngfelt, A., Makuch, Z., Mangano, E., Porter, R. T. J., Pourkashanian, M., Rochelle, G. T., Shah, N., ... Fennell, P. S. (2013). Carbon capture and storage update. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 7(1), 130–189. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C3EE42350F>
9. European Commission. (2021). Carbon capture, storage and utilisation. https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/oil-gas-and-coal/carbon-capture-storage-and-utilisation_en
10. IEA. (2019, September). Putting CO₂ to Use . <https://www.iea.org/reports/putting-co2-to-use>
11. IEA. (2022, October). Global energy-related CO₂ emissions by sector. <https://www.iea.org/data-and-statistics/charts/global-energy-related-co2-emissions-by-sector>
12. IEA. (2020). The role of CCUS in low-carbon power systems.
13. Luderer, G., Vrontisi, Z., Bertram, C., Edelenbosch, O. Y., Pietzcker, R. C., Rogelj, J., de Boer, H. S., Drouet, L., Emmerling, J., Fricko, O., Fujimori, S., Havlík, P., Iyer, G., Keramidas, K., Kitous, A., Pehl, M., Krey, V., Riahi, K., Saveyn, B., ... Kriegler, E. (2018). Residual fossil CO₂ emissions in 1.5–2 °C pathways. *Nature Climate Change* 2018 8:7, 8(7), 626–633. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0198-6>
14. Müller, L. J., Kätelhön, A., Bringezu, S., McCoy, S., Suh, S., Edwards, R., Sick, V., Kaiser, S., Cuéllar-Franca, R., el Khamlichi, A., Lee, J. H., von der Assen, N., & Bardow, A. (2020). The carbon footprint of the carbon feedstock CO₂. *Energy and Environmental Science*, 13(9), 2979–2992. <https://doi.org/10.1039/d0ee01530j>
15. Kätelhön, A., Meys, R., Deutz, S., Suh, S., & Bardow, A. (2019). Climate change mitigation potential of carbon capture and utilisation in the chemical industry. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 166(23), 11187–11194. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1821029116>
16. Konietzko, J. (2021). How can we embrace the complexity of the sustainability transition, without getting stuck in carbon tunnel vision? . https://www.linkedin.com/posts/jankonietzko_climatechange-cop26-circulareconomy-activity-6859418054867083264-EMPG/
17. CO₂ Value Europe. (2022, December). EU Reaches First Milestone Agreements on Fit-for-55, with Key Provisions for CCU. <https://co2value.eu/eu-reaches-first-milestone-agreements-on-fit-for-55-with-key-provisions-for-ccu/>
18. European Commission. (2023, March). The Net-Zero Industry Act: Accelerating the transition to climate neutrality. https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/industry/sustainability/net-zero-industry-act_en
19. CO₂ Value Europe. (2023, April). REDIII and FuelEU Maritime: EU Sends a Clear Signal on CCU Fuels and Green Hydrogen in Transport and Industry. <https://co2value.eu/rediii-and-fueleu-maritime-eu-sends-a-clear-signal-on-ccu-fuels-and-green-hydrogen-in-transport-and-industry/>
20. European Commission. (2021). Proposal for a REGULATION OF THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND OF THE COUNCIL on ensuring a level playing field for sustainable air transport. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52021PC0561>
21. European Parliament. (2023, April). Fit for 55: Parliament and Council reach deal on greener aviation fuels. <https://www.europarl.europa.eu/news/en/press-room/20230424IPR82023/fit-for-55-parliament-and-council-reach-deal-on-greener-aviation-fuels>
22. European Commission. (2022). Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council establishing a Union certification framework for carbon removals. Brussels, 30.11.2022.
23. SBTi. (2022). Cement science based target setting guidance.
24. The European Union. (2022). A European Green Deal. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/priorities-2019-2024/european-green-deal_en

25. The European Union. (2020, March). Changing how we produce and consume: New Circular Economy Action Plan shows the way to a climate-neutral, competitive economy of empowered consumers.
https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/ip_20_420
26. BEIS. (2021). Government Response to Carbon Capture Usage and Storage: Market Engagement on Cluster Sequencing.
27. BEIS. (2021). May 2021 CCUS Supply Chains: a roadmap to maximise the UK's potential.
28. Lamb, K. J., & Styring, P. (2022). Perspectives for the circular chemical economy post COP26. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 10. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2022.1079010>
29. UK Gov. (2023). UK Net Zero Research and Innovation Framework: Delivery Plan 2022-2025.
30. US Gov. (2023). Inflation Reduction Act guidebook.
31. US DOE. (2023). The Infrastructure Investment and Jobs Act Factsheet.
32. NBC News. (2023, July). Biden admin seeks to jumpstart carbon recycling with \$100 million in grants.
<https://www.nbcnews.com/science/environment/biden-admin-seeks-jumpstart-carbon-recycling-100-million-grants-rcna96891>
33. Newman, A. J. K., Dowson, G. R. M., Platt, E. G., Handford-Styring, H. J., & Styring, P. (2023). Custodians of carbon: creating a circular carbon economy. *Frontiers in Energy Research*, 11. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenrg.2023.1124072>
34. Bellamy, R., & Raimi, K. T. (2023). Communicating carbon removal. *Frontiers in Climate*, 5.
<https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2023.1205388>
35. IEA. (2020). Energy Technology Perspectives 2020. www.iea.org/t&c/
36. DG Ener. (2020). LCA4CCU Guidelines for Life Cycle Assessment of Carbon Capture and Utilisation.